

Reactions of (continued)

ARC14636	"	MR	MR	S	S
ARC14766	"	R	R	S	R
ARC14950B	"	MR	S	R	S
A-1	"	R	MR	R	R
ADR52	"	R	MR	R	R
Chemban	"	MR	R	R	S
Chempan	"	R	R	S	R
Chemparampandi	"	R	R	S	S
Chennellu	"	R	R	R	R
Chennirayenam	"	R	MR	R	S
Cheriya Chittari	"	R	R	S	S
Chittari	"	R	MR	S	R
Chuvanna kumbolan	"	MR	MR	R	S
Eswara Mangalam	"	R	R	S	S
GS 531	"	R	R	S	S
Kodiyam	"	MR	R	S	S
Kula peruvula	"	R	MR	S	S
LXH/2-281	"	R	R	S	R
Lalbasumati	"	R	R	S	S
Luangu	Vietnam	R	S	S	R
Mawee	Sri Lanka	R	MR	S	R
Malalwariyan	"	MR	S	R	R
Mudukiriyal	"	R	R	S	S
Pandi	India	R	R	R	R
Parakulam	"	R	S	R	S
Podwi-A8	Sri Lanka	R	R	S	S
PTB247	India	R	MR	S	R
PTB12	"	MR	S	R	R
PTB19	"	R	R	R	R
PTB21	"	R	R	R	R
PTB33	"	R	R	S	S
PTB33A	"	R	R	S	R
S 61	"	R	S	S	R
Siam 7	"	R	MR	S	R
Sulai	Sri Lanka	MR	MR	S	R
T 10	India	R	S	R	S
T 12	"	R	S	S	R
T 16	"	R	S	R	S
T 27	"	R	S	S	R
T 1415	"	R	S	S	R
T 1421	"	R	S	S	R
T 1425	"	MR	R	R	S
T 1426	"	R	MR	R	R
T 1432	"	R	S	R	S
T 1471	"	R	R	R	R
T 1477	"	MR	R	S	R
T 2755	"	MR	S	S	R
Valsara Champara	"	R	R	R	R
Vella Chenipan	"	R	S	R	R
Vellathil Cheera	"	R	R	R	R
Vellai Langayan	"	MR	R	S	S
Vellutha cheera	"	R	MR	R	S
W 128	"	MR	S	S	R
AC No. 710	"	MR	S	R	R
AC No. 5352	"	R	R	S	S
AC No. 8895	"	R	S	S	R

^a BPH = brown planthopper, WBPH = whitebacked planthopper, CM = gall midge, RTV = rice tungro virus, R = resistant, S = susceptible, MR = moderately resistant.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Cold tolerance

Cold-tolerant rice in Bangladesh

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During the 1979 transplanted aman season, 113 lines were screened at BRRI for cold tolerance at the reproductive stage. The experimental materials were seeded on 14 August and planted on 15 September 1979. Each line was planted in a 5.4-m-long plot with 4 rows spaced 25 × 15 cm, using 1 seedling/hill. The resistant check (China 1039) and the susceptible check (1R8) were planted after every 10th plot. Fertilizer was applied at 90-65-45 kg NPK/ha with a split of N (50% + 25% + 25%). During the reproductive phase, the temperature ranged from 27.3° to 13.7° C. Considering panicle emergence, flowering uniformity, sterility, and yield, the following lines were selected:

BK51-282-8/HR5, BR51-282-8/HR26, BR51-282-8/HR34, HP46 (HPV13), IR7682-135-3-2, IR8866-26-2, IR8866-30-2, IR8866-30-3, and IR3941-27-1. ■

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